

Effectiveness of health services after obtaining accreditation of quality in health centers of Makkah city

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ABSTRACT

In developing countries, accreditation is increasingly being used as a tool for government regulation to guarantee quality of healthcare. The aim of this study was to evaluate the impact of accreditation programs on the quality of healthcare services on males and females with their level of satisfaction in five primary health centers (PHC) situated in Makkah city. It also aims to determine the health services preferred by the respondents of both genders in these five centers after obtaining quality standards recently. The study selected five healthcare centers namely prosperous Al-Zahir PHC, Al-Nuwaria PHC, Al-Adel PHC, Al-Aziza PHC, Kuwdi and Al-Hijra PHC. These five healthcare centers obtained accreditation of quality by the Central Board for Accreditation of Healthcare Institutions (CBAHI) in Saudi Arabia. The current study included 250 reviewers, which represent a random sample of the population in the holy capital city. Where 50 questionnaires were distributed to each of these centers (25 male and 25 female) to see their complaints and to know trends and opinions about the service provided for them from the healthcare centers. It was observed from the study that the health centers who obtained accreditation improved the health services leading to the reduction of medical problems and errors, and the improvement and development of the work environment.

Introduction

The Accreditation programs have been increasing and spreading throughout the world from developed to developing countries from the past three decades, and today there are several accreditation programs for healthcare organizations. In developing countries, accreditation is increasingly being used as a tool for government regulation to guarantee quality of healthcare.

Quality standards for hospitals and other medical facilities were first introduced in the Saudi Arabia in the 'Minimum Standard for Hospitals' developed in 2005. The Central Board for Accreditation of Healthcare Institutions (CBAHI) in Saudi Arabia was formed in 2005 based on the recommendation of the Council of Health Services in Saudi Arabia. CBAHI was established to formulate and implement quality Standards in all health sectors all over the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (CBAHI web site).

The accreditation of healthcare institutions in its early stages requires the preparation and development of healthcare standards, including all steps and stages of the administrative and technical work, which must be prepared and developed and tested always by international and local experts, and without stopping. And also requires the preparation and development of manpower to train and guide

the health facilities of all kinds, to make health standards as part of the routine daily work; and a great part of this stage has been completed, but what is coming is of no less important than what has been accomplished in the past. (Khoja, 2011):

However, while accreditation standards have been implemented more widely over the past 40 years, and the probability of receiving safe and high-quality health care has increased for patients worldwide (Pomey et al. 2010), it is not clear whether accreditation programmes truly improve health organisations, services or clinical care (Greenfield et al. 2012).

Majority of past researches conducted on late decade in developed and developing countries investigated impact of accreditation programs on healthcare organizations related to its structures, processes, outcomes and patient satisfaction were highly great positive impact. Most researchers had targeted nursing staff in their populations and samples to determine the impact of accreditation programs on healthcare services, because of its vital role on quality and safety of healthcare's services.

Although Saudi Arabia implementing quality standards through accreditation policies since 2005, little is known about its impact on stakeholder assessment of the provision of healthcare.

Therefore the study was conducted to determine the quality of healthcare services provided by accredited five hospitals of Makkah city on the basis of the views of reviewers. In addition, this study aimed to explore the level of satisfaction in five health centers situated in Makkah city and the health services preferred by the reviewers of both genders after obtaining quality standards recently.

Materials and Methods

Study design

Across sectional descriptive study was conducted at 5 primary healthcare centers (PHC) of Makkah city. The centers were Al-Zahir PHC, Al-Nuwaria PHC, Al-Adel PHC, Al-Aziza PHC, Kuwdi and Al-Hijra PHC and accredited recently. The study was conducted during the period from January to November, 2020 in Makkah city of Saudi Arabia.

Selection of respondents

The patients who were taking health services from these five PHC were selected for this study as respondents. Both male and female were included in this study. The average age of the male and female was 30 to 45 years)

Data collection and analysis

With due permission from the PHC authority, data were collected from the respondents through a

structured questionnaire. The questionnaire includes six questions, of which three questions are closed and three were open-ended questions. The first question was about the level of satisfaction (satisfied, somewhat satisfied, not satisfied) of the respondents while taking health care services. The second and third questions were, whether the respondents were happy and unhappy with the health services. The fourth question was whether there was recoding system of writing official complaints or non-official. The fifth question was on level of satisfaction (satisfied, somewhat satisfied, not satisfied) of the respondents about cleaning services in PHCs. The last question was from writing proposals and expectations of the services provided by the health center to developing and work improvement in future.

The analysis of the results was prepared in Excel program of office 2010, histogram graphics, and results have been presented in the study by using frequency tables, percentages, and graphs.

Result and Discussion

The women and men respondents that participated in this survey from Alzahirphc and Alaziza HPC were 55% and 45%. In Alnawaria it was 52% and 48%. Whereas in Adel the female respondents were 75% and men were 25%. In Kuwdi and Alhijra it was 51% and 49%.

Table 1: Number of respondents from each health care center

Women (n)	Alzahir	Alnawaria	Aladel	Alaziza	Kuwdi and Alhijra
10-16	0	0	3	0	2
17-30	10	5	8	10	9
31-45	6	13	13	6	14
Above 45	1	9	6	1	4
latoT	17(55%)	27(52%)	30(75%)	17(55%)	29 (51%)
neM(n)					
10-16	0	0	0	0	3
17-30	8	3	3	8	12
31-45	6	8	4	6	9
Above 45	0	14	3	0	4
latoT	14(45%)	25(48%)	10(25%)	14 (45%)	28 (49%)

The average age of female and male respondents was 30 to 45 years.

At Al-Zahir Health Center, among the respondents it was observed that 72% were satisfied with health services, 13.9% (11.6% men 2.3% women) had

somewhat satisfaction. Whereas no satisfaction of both male and female respondents was recorded in Al-Nuwaria PHC.

For Al-Adel PHC, 26% men were satisfied with health services and there were no cases of somewhat

satisfaction or dissatisfaction among them. While 73% and 7% respondents were found for satisfied somewhat satisfied with the health services. Nobody was found with dissatisfaction.

For Al-Aziza PHC 51.6% men were found satisfied with the health services and 3% satisfied somewhat and no dissatisfied respondents were found among them. The percentage of women satisfied was 38.7%, 3% for dissatisfaction and satisfaction somewhat, respectively.

For Kuwdi and Al-Hijra PHC, the level of satisfaction among men were 40%, 7.2% for satisfaction somewhat and no dissatisfaction, while satisfied and somewhat satisfied women were 49%, 3%, respectively.

The quality of health services in different sectors was also recorded. In Al-Zahir PHC, male respondents for clinics 60%, nursing 46%, administration 38%, pharmacy 36%, doctors 34%, reception 33%, 31% for both teeth and laboratory, and finally 29% for both radiology and vaccinations were happy with these service sectors (Figure 1). Whereas for women for management 9%, and 8% for a reception and 6% for a nurse, clinic, dental, laboratory, x-ray, pharmacy, doctors and vaccinations were happy (Figure 2).

With health services at Al-Nuwaria PHC among the the male respondent 46% were happy for nurse, 42% clinics, 36% for dental, cleaning and pharmacy, 34% for x-ray, reception and management, laboratory and 32% for vaccination and 29% for doctors (Figure 1). While the health services satisfied women in this PHC were 40% for clinics, 35% for nursing, 31% for pharmacy, 30% for vaccinations and cleaning, 29% for teeth,

laboratory, X-rays, reception and management and 25% for doctors (Figure 2).

At Al-Adel PHC, among the male respondent 55% were happy for clinics, reception 23%, doctors and x-ray by 21%, and 18% for nurse, dental, laboratory, pharmacy and management, and for vaccinations 13% (Figure 1). On the other hand among women respondent 54% were happy for clinics, 52% reception, 51% nurse and doctors, 30% for pharmacy, laboratory 23%, 17% for dental, management 12%, 10% for vaccinations and finally 9% for x-ray (Figure 2).

With the health services provided by Al- Aziza PHC, among male respondents 35% were happy for clinics, 25% for dentists, 15% for the pharmacy, 12% for doctors, and 3% for nursing, and there was no satisfaction with the health services related to the laboratory, radiology, reception, management, vaccinations and cleaning (Figure 1) Whereas among female respondents 29% were happy for clinics, 18% for nurse, 12% for pharmacy, 3% for doctors, and no health services satisfaction for laboratory, x-ray, reception, management, vaccinations and cleaning (Figure 2).

With the health services provided by Kuwdi and Al-Hijra PHC, among the male respondent 89% were happy for clinics, 22% for the dentists, 21% for the reception, 17% for both nursing and vaccinations, 16% for radiology and pharmacy, while 15% for each of the doctors, laboratory, management, cleaning (Figure 1). While among female respondents 96% were happy for clinics, 30% for teeth, 26% for vaccinations, 22% for each of the nursing, doctors, laboratory, x-ray, reception, pharmacy, management, vaccinations and cleaning (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Satisfaction among men in PHCs

Figure 2: Satisfaction among women in PHCs

Regarding the the fourth question on repondent's submission with an official or verbal complaint of poor services at Al-Zahir PHC, we found that the percentage of men who filed complaints was 15.6%, while those who did not was 39.5%, and for women who did not submit a complaint it was 34.9%. while 9.6% of women filled complaints. In Alnawaria PHC we find that the percentage of men who filed complaints was 11% and non-complaints 36%, while women who submit a complaint was 14.8%, and the non-applicants were 38%. In the Al Adel PHC, the number of respondent who have filed complaints was 7% and 19.1% did not. While women filled a complaint about 7%, and 66% did not complained. For Alaziza PHC men who filed complaints were 43%, while those who did not were 3%. While women who submitted complaint were 32%, and 22% did not. At Kuwdi & Al-Hijra PHC, we find that the percentage of men who filed complaints was 5.4%, while those who did not, was 43.8%. Among women who filed complaints were 1.8%, while those who did not, was 49 %.

Regarding submitting proposals and opinions to develop work in Al-Zahir PHC, 9.3% of men said that they did, while 32.5% of them said, they did not.

Table 1: The percentage of applicants and non-complaints from both genders in the five PHCs

PHCs	Men		Women	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
Alzahir	15.6%	39.5%	9.6%	34.9%
Alnawaria	11%	36%	14.8%	38%
Aladel	7%	19.1%	7%	66%
Alaziza	43%	3%	32%	22%
Kuwdi & Al-Hijra	5.4%	43.8%	1.8%	49%

Regarding the proposal or suggestion to develop the services by the provided the male respondents 7% men complanined whereas no complained was made by 18% respondents. While for female respondents it was 5% by complained respondent and 65% for non-complained respondent in Al-Adel PHC. For Al-Aziza PHC, male respondent complained was 45% and female was 32.2%, while 3% men and 22% of women did not complain.

For men who submitted proposals/suggestion and opinions to develop work in Kuwdi & Al-Hijra PHC was 5%, while 1% was women. The male respondents were 41% and female respondents were 49% women who did not complained.

Conclusions

It was observed from the study that the health centers who obtained accreditation improved the health services leading to the reduction of medical problems and errors, and the improvement and development of the work environment.

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